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THE APENNINE SIBYL

A MYSTERY AND A LEGEND

A MYSTERIOUS QUOTE FROM «BISHOP PRIMUS CAMBILUNENSIS» UNVEILED¹

1. Fortunato Ciucci and his words on the Cave of Norcia

The legend of an Apennine Sibyl residing beneath a remote peak in central Italy has journeyed across many European countries, spanning more than six centuries and emerging in unexpected ways in the works of dozens of authors speaking different languages.

One of the most cryptic quotes on the Sibyl of the Apennines which scholars have dealt with is found in an historical essay written in year 1650 by Father Fortunato Ciucci, a monk who lived in Norcia, the town which is set in the vicinity of Mount Sibyl. In his *Chronicles of the Antique Town of Norsia* (*Historie dell'antica città di Norsia* in Italian), Father Ciucci reports the following sentence:

«Not far from the said Lakes [of Mount Vettore], on the southern side of the same mountain, a frightful Cavern is present, in which since time immemorial [...] a false Sibyl has her abode, whom Primus Cambilunensis, a Bishop and Theologist of the Topography of the holy martyrs, maintains she is the Emerian, also known as Cimmerian, a different Sibyl from the Cumaean and the Tiburtine, with the following words: 'The Emerian Sibyl, who some call Cimmerian owing to the gloominess of her abode, and who resides in the Cave of Norcia, not the same Sibyl as the Cumaean and the Tiburtine'».

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(http://www.italianwriter.it/TheApennineSibyl/TheApennineSibyl_SibylsApennine.asp)

[In the original Italian text: «Non molto lontano dai detti Laghi [del Monte Vettore] verso il Mezzogiorno nell'Istesso Monte Vittore s'apre un'orrenda Spelonca, dove da un lungo rivolgimento di tempo [...] abita una mensogniera Sibilla, la quale dice Primo Cambilunense Vescovo e Teologo della Topografia de' santi martiri che sia l'Emeria chiamata Cimeria, diversa dalla Cumea, e Tiburtina, con queste parole: 'Sybillam Emericam quam alij Cimeriam vocant ab obscuritate loci, et in Nursinis Antris habitantem, atque a Cumea, et a Tiburtina diversam»].

Fig. 1 - An artist's impression of Father Fortunato Ciucci noting down his words about the Sibyl's cave, together with a vista on Mount Sibyl

A number of questions arise when confronting with Father Ciucci's antique excerpt: who was «Primus Cambilunensis», bishop and theologian? What sort of 'Topography' about martyrs is the book Father Ciucci is quoting from? Who is the 'Cimmerian Sibyl' and why that Sibyl would be connected to the Sibyl of the Apennines?

For centuries, this mysterious, enigmatic reference to the Sibyl of Norcia has rested unfathomed before the puzzled eyes of scholars, in the absence of a clue as to where to turn in order to find the original source of Ciucci's quote.

Today, “The Apennine Sibyl - A Mystery and a Legend” is proud to bring all the interlocking pieces of this astounding literary puzzle together. Like in a most classical treasure hunt, we will analyse each clue available to us, searching into history and literature, so that in the end we will be fully able to reassemble the whole picture and confer an identity and an epoch to

Primus Cambilunensis: another element of the amazing portrait of the Apennine Sibyl that has been painted from many different hands across many centuries throughout the lands of Europe.

Follow me into this thrilling journey across old books and ancient manuscripts, a travel through a legend that never stops dispensing new surprises.

2. A sixteenth-century “Topographia Martyrum” from Sicily (with the Sibyl of Norcia included)

In 1650 Father Fortunato Ciucci reported that in an essay written by a certain «Primus Cambilunensis» the Sibyl of Norcia was mentioned as living in a gloomy cave in the Sibillini Mountain Range.

But who was «Primus Cambilunensis», and where can we trace his book?

If we look for an author named 'Primus' in the European literature of the seventeenth century, or of earlier centuries, we find that we cannot pinpoint a specific writer who bears this name. To restrict our search, a helpful indication may come from the word «Cambilunensis», a geographical qualifier which indicates the ancient French town of Chalon-sur-Saône, attested as 'Cavillonum' or 'Cabillonum' in Julius Ceasar's *Gallic War*.

According to Father Ciucci, «Primus Cambilunensis» was a bishop and author of theological essays, so we may try and address the list of bishops that have held the post in Chalon-sur-Saône from early Middle Ages to year 1650, when the monk from Norcia noted down his quote. However, this list, known from the works by other scholars, is quite long: restraining ourselves to the eleventh century and onwards, it starts from a certain Lambert in year 1017 and continues with Geoffroy, Hugues, Guy, Aicard and many others, up to Cyrus de Thiard de Bissy and Jacques de Neuchèze in the first half of the seventeenth century, the age of Father Ciucci. None of such bishops is named 'Primus' and none of them appears, at least at a first glance, to have ever written any essay on martyrs, as stated by Ciucci.

So we got stuck in a sort of dead end. The list of Chalon-sur-Saône's bishops offers us no hints. Our hunt seems to end up in a small town of Eastern France, and the words written in Norcia by Father Fortunato Ciucci in 1650 appear to be doomed to a sad destiny of unsubstantiality and oblivion.

Yet a very remarkable clue comes to our aid.

Someone, at some point in history, did actually write and publish an essay on martyrs and the places where their martyrdoms happened: a 'Topography of Martyrs', exactly what Ciucci seems to have drawn is quote from.

We have to leave France, at least for the time being, and turn to sixteenth-century Italy. In the town of Messina, lying on the easternmost tip of Sicily right in front of the renowned strait, once lived a famous historian, astronomer and mathematician, a benedictine abbot who was known in Europe as a learned scholar: Francesco Maurolico.

A man of great erudition, he was the author of a *Martyrologium*, a work providing information on saints and martyrs of the Catholic Church for each day of the year, a sort of handbook for priests celebrating the Mass. However, our interest is not in this part of his book.

Maurolico's *Martyrologium*, published in Venice in 1568, contains an addendum which is fully relevant to our search. In fact, in the final section of his work Maurolico includes a specific list of places: an inventory of sites, towns and regions, starting from Antiochia in Syria and ending up with Urçi, today's Almeria in Spain, and also containing additional sites pertaining to apostles, prophets and other characters from the Holy Bible.

The title of this section is *Topographia Sanctorum Christi Martyrum*: exactly the «Topography of the holy martyrs» mentioned by Father Fortunato Ciucci in his *Chronicles of the Antique Town of Norsia* a century later.

And this is not all. It is Francesco Maurolico himself who adds a subheading to that title: he states that his *Topographia* is drawn from «Primus Cabilunensis, bishop and theologian, once composed in the Year of

Salvation 1450 and now at last complemented» [in the original Latin text: «per Primum Cabilunensem, episcopum, ac theologum, Anno salutis MCCCCL olim composita Et nunc demum recognita»].

Fig. 2 - Francesco Maurolico's *Martyrologium*, original edition published in Venice in 1568, with the addendum on the *Topographia Sanctorum Christi Martyrum*

Here we are. We have possibly found the original source from which Father Fortunato Ciucci, a benedictine monk active in Norcia around 1650, extracted his words about the Sibyl and her cave.

We will see that our surmise is absolutely correct. Because Francesco Maurolico, who says he is reporting words from an earlier author named Primus, provides the same sentences subsequently reported by Ciucci.

And our finding is even richer than that: “The Apennine Sibyl - A Mystery and a Legend” is proud to convey to the attention of contemporary scholars the additional, previously-unknown sentences that Maurolico wrote about the Sibyl. Actually, there is more than one. As we will see in the next paragraph.

3. The Sibyl looms through the words written by Francesco Maurolico

Francesco Maurolico, a man of the late Renaissance, a benedictine abbot, one of the most learned scholars in Messina during the first half of the sixteenth century. Many of his works have never been published and are now lost to us; many others have reached our present times, including scientific essays like the *Opuscula Mathematica*, historical chronicles such as the *Sicanicarum Rerum Compendium*, and religious works as the *Topographia Sanctorum Christi Martyrum*, contained in his *Martyrologium*.

It is in the *Topographia* that we find a number of mentions concerning the Sibyl of Norcia: three different references which cast a new, unprecedented light upon the sibilline oracle that, according to the legend, resides beneath the peak of Mount Sibyl, in central Italy.

In this article, for the first time ever, we publish the three mentions of the Sibyl of Norcia written by Francesco Maurolico in 1568.

A first mention is provided by Maurolico at the very beginning of his alphabetical list of places which are relevant to martyrs. Here is what he notes down under letter 'A':

«Ameria, an Italian town set in the Sabine region. From this town the author names the 'Emerian Sibyl', who others call the 'Cimeriam' owing to the uncertainty of the place; she lives in the caverns of Norcia, and it is different from both the Cumaean and the Tiburtine Sibyls».

[In the original Latin text: «Ameria civitas Italiae in Sabinis. Hinc denominat author Sybillam Emeriam, quam alii Cimeriam vocant ab obscuritate loci, et in Nurcinis antris habitantem, atque a Cumana, et a Tyburtina diversam»].

The above excerpt is quite puzzling: Maurolico refers to a Sibyl who lives «in the caverns of Norcia», but he also mentions another Italian town, Amelia (whose Latin name is 'Ameria'). Though the latter is not far from Norcia and lies in the same ancient region of Sabine, Amelia, a town which still stands, is set in a different geographical area, separated from Norcia by a number of mountainous ridges, and definitely it has nothing to do with the Sibillini Mountain Range.

A second notable trait comes in sight either: Francesco Maurolico calls the Sibyl of Norcia 'Emeriam' or 'Cimeriam': a Sibyl that appears in some versions of the most classical enumeration of Sibyls provided by Lucius Caecilius Firmianus Lactantius, a fourth-century author. Does Maurolico maintain that the Apennine Sibyl actually belongs to the list of ten classical Sibyl known from antiquity?

But Maurolico does not restrict himself to a single mention. Under letter 'N' in his *Topographia*, we find another mention. And, this time, 'N' is for 'Norcia':

«Norcia, a town of the Italian region of Picenum; close to it is the Cavern of the Cimeriam Sibyl, and the lake of Demons».

[In the original Latin text: «Nurcia civitas Italiae in agro Piceno, iuxta quam est Antrum Sibyllae Cymeriae, et lacus Daemonum»].

Again, Maurolico stresses the point that the name of the Sibyl of Norcia is 'Cimeriam': once more, a direct reference to the classical list of ten Sibyls.

That was the second mention. However, there is a third too. At all appearances, the Sicilian abbot had a special interest in Sibyls, as later in his *Topographia* he introduces a specific section specifically dedicated to the sibilline oracles, «On Sibyls and other authors» [in the original Latin text: «De Sibyllis, et variis Authoribus»]. In this section, Maurolico provides quotes from a number of classical authors who wrote about the Sibyls. When it comes to Lactantius, he enumerates the ten Sibyls included in the renowned classical list. The fourth in the list is the one we are interested in:

«The fourth Sibyl is the Cumaeam, whom Naevius mentions in his books about the Punic war, and Piso in his annals as well», says Maurolico, reporting the same words that are actually found in most versions of fourth-century Lactantius' *De divinis institutionibus*.

However, the learned Sicilian abbot adds further words, which are not present in Lactantius' original excerpt:

«... from the Cimeriam castle, also known as the Cave of Norcia, which some call by the corrupted name of 'Cymeia' or 'Cymica'».

[In the original Latin text: «ex Cimerio oppido, sive Antro nurcino, quae corrupto forte verbo Cymeia, vel Cymica vocetur a nonnullis»].

Ameria, Emeriam, Cimeriam, Cymeriam, Cymeia, Cymica, Cumaeam: a plethora of different qualifiers, which - according to Francesco Maurolico - would all point to a same oracle: the Sibyl of Norcia, which is not the one from Cumae (for Lactantius, and Maurolico as well, the latter is listed as the seventh Sibyl, with the Latin qualifiers «Cumanam» and also «Amaltheam»).

Now uncertainty has reached its utmost level. Where did Maurolico take all those words from? Did he really quote, as he explicitly declares, from a certain «Primus Cabilunensis, bishop and theologian» and his work allegedly written in 1450? Who is the Cimeriam Sibyl? And has she really anything to do with our Sibyl of the Apennines, as alleged by Maurolico?

Fig. 3 - Three mentions about the Sibyl of Norcia found in Francesco Maurolico's *Topographia Sanctorum Christi Martyrum*

We will try to provide an answer to all such questions in the next article, when we will find out the true identity of «Primus Cabilunensis», and we will read directly from the pages of his work.

Does Primus also provide mentions about the Sibyl of Norcia? Or, did Maurolico just «complemented» Primus' work by inserting his own words concerning our Sibyl?

We will check it out in the next paragraphs.

4. In search of the shadowy identity of 'Primus'

Now the time has come to unveil the identity of 'Primus Cambilunensis', allegedly the original source from which Francesco Maurolico, in 1568, extracted a number of cryptic mentions about the Apennine Sibyl, and also the «bishop and theologian» quoted by Father Fortunato Ciucci from Norcia who, a century later, in 1650, reported a similar mention concerning the same Sibyl.

We know that 'Primus' is connected to Chalon-sur-Saône, the ancient French town of 'Cabillonum'. Furthermore, we know that he was a bishop, though no bishop with such name is listed in the historical records of Chalon-sur-Saône. Finally, we know that in 1450 he wrote some kind of 'Topography of Martyrs', as attested in both Ciucci and Maurolico.

So who is 'Primus'?

We are about to follow so faint a trace that it seems quite impossible we have any chance to succeed. However, you will see that we will finally get through. Let's start and find out who 'Primus Cambilunensis' was.

As a matter of fact, we are able to positively retrieve an additional excerpt which does mention our unknown Primus.

Let's turn to the antique pages of a most precious book: the *Cosmographia* of second-century Roman-Greek author Claudius Ptolemaeus (Ptolemy in modern English). However, we are not going to address the ancient extant manuscripts, written in Greek. We want to read from a later, particularly rare printed version, namely the one published in Latin by Johann Reger, in Ulm, a German town, in 1486.

Reger's version begins with an alphabetical list of places, including information which is not to be ascribed to Ptolemy, as it manifestly refers directly to Reger's age. And, under letter 'C', we find a place whose name is «Cabulium»: this is nothing else than 'Cabillonum', or, in our modern times, Chalon-sur-Saône.

Fig. 4 - The excerpt on Cabulium as it appears in Johann Reger's *Cosmographia* from Ptolemy, a book published in Ulm in 1486

What does Reger write about «Cabulium»? Here are his precise words:

«Cabulium [...] Here [was] the noble Primus, German bishop and professor of sacred theology, who in the year of our Lord 1450 arranged the saints in his world map, which is called a spiritual one».

[In the original Latin text: «Cabulium [...] Hic dominus primus germani episcopus sacre theologie professor qui anno domini 1450 hos sanctos composuit in sua mappa mundi que spiritualis dicitur»].

We are getting closer and closer to our target: in Chalon-sur-Saône, in 1450, someone composed a 'world map of saints', the same kind of literary work attributed to 'Primus' by Ciucci and Maurolico, and he was a «German bishop».

Now, if we peruse the list of bishops who held the post in Chalon-sur-Saône throughout the centuries, we find that between 1436 and 1461 the position was occupied by a Jean Germain. He was a scholar and an author of pious literary works. His family name was 'Germain': even though he was not German (he was born in Cluny), its surname sounds like the «German bishop» mentioned by Reger.

However, his name was 'Jean', not 'Primus'. So what shall we do with this unfit name?

To solve the riddle, we have to draw on another remarkable book, a posthumous work published in 1725, written by a certain Adrien Baillet, an erudite and priest who lived in Paris in the second half of the seventeenth century. His *Scholarly Opinions on the Main Works of the Writers* (*Jugemens des Savans sur les Principaux Ouvrages des Auteurs*) is a quite unbelievable, mammoth collection, made up of eight books, of literary criticism applied to all sorts of writers and poets, starting from classical authors and up to Baillet's age.

In Book 5, Baillet explores the world of the «Authors in disguise» [«Les auteurs déguisés»] by listing hundreds and hundreds of 'noms de plume' for just as much authors. And, under letter 'P', we find the following pen name:

«Primus: Jean Germain».

Fig. 5 - Adrien Baillet's *Jugemens des Savans* (1725) containing the link between Jean Germain and 'Primus'

There we are. We got it. At last we discovered the true identity of «Primus Cambilunensis»: he is Jean Germain, bishop of Chalon-sur-Saône from 1436 to 1461, whose pen name was 'Primus'.

As a matter of fact, “The Apennine Sibyl - A Mystery and a Legend” is not first in achieving such result, as it had already been stated by other scholars (Baudouin de Gaiffier and Gabriel Le Bras in the first half of the twentieth century); however, the fanciful steps we have been retracing - from Fortunato Ciucci to Francesco Maurolico, from Johann Reger's edition of Ptolemy's *Cosmographia* to Adrien Baillet's ponderous work - are fully original: a treasure hunt carried out across various different authors and centuries.

Now, to crosscheck our guess, we only need to inspect whether Jean Germain, the fifteenth-century French bishop, did actually write and publish any 'Topography of Martyrs'.

He did. In 1449, he composed a *Spiritual Worldmap* (*Mappemonde Spirituelle* in French), containing information on which places were made holy by saints, apostles and martyrs with their presence, sermons and deeds.

So we are now about to open Jean Germain's *Worldmap* and see whether we can find in it any reference to Norcia and the Apennine Sibyl, as alleged by Fortunato Ciucci and Francesco Maurolico. Nobody has ever read the work of Jean Germain with the intention of performing such a check.

Let's see what happens.

5. The "*Mappemonde Spirituelle*" by Jean Germain

«Jehan Germain, professor of theology in Paris and by the grace of God bishop of Chalon-sur-Saône, [...] Chancellor of the Golden Fleece, in honour and homage. As many have already portrayed many different wordly maps by indicating in them the regions and countries and towns and castles and the seas [...], beasts and snakes and birds and fish and monsters to exhibit the wonders of the world [...] we made up in the year of the Lord 1449 this world map which, in contrast to the others, might be called a spiritual one».

[In the old French text: «Jehan Germain, docteur en theologie a Paris par la grace de dieu evesque de Chalon sur la Soone [...] Chancellier de [l']ordre de la tousein dor, tout honneur and reverence. Que'en consideration que plusieurs se sont occupez a portraire diverses mappemondes temporelles et en illes ont consigné les provinces, pays, aucunes citez, villes, chasteaulx, mers [...] bestes, serpens, oyseaulx, poissons et monstres alfin se congnoistre les merveilles du monde [...] Avons l'an de notre seigneur 1449 fait cette mappemonde et icelle a la difference des autres appeller spirituelle»].

This is the opening of the *Spiritual Worldmap* (*Mappemonde Spirituelle*) written by Jean Germain - which we know under the pen name «Primus Cambilunensis» - in the fifteenth century: a work that intended to convey the picture of a physical world in which God had performed sacred deeds

through his holy heralds, including apostles, martyrs, priests and blessed maidens («apôtres, les plus nommés martyrs, confesseurs, vierges»).

Fig. 6 - Jean Germain's *Mappemonde Spirituelle* from manuscript Français 13235 (Bibliothèque Nationale de France)

Did Jean Germain include an Apennine Sibyl in his geography of hallowed preachers and announcers of the Salvation scattered all around the known world? Abbot Francesco Maurolico in the sixteenth century and Father Fortunato Ciucci in the seventeenth alleged that the French bishop actually mentioned a Sibyl of Norcia in his *Mappemonde*. Is that true?

To find out, we need to address one of the five extant manuscripts of Germain's *Spiritual Worldmap*, such as the illuminated manuscript from Lyon, from which we draw the fine miniature which shows the bishop of Chalons-sur-Saône presenting his work to Duke Philip the Good of Burgundy; or the instance preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France (Département des Manuscrits, Français 13235).

Fig. 7 - The fine miniature contained in the manuscript of Jean Germain's *Mappemonde Spirituelle* preserved at the Bibliothèque Municipale de Lyon (P.A. 032)

Let's go through the pages of the latter: Jean Germain brings us across Arabia, Syria, Judea, Cappadocia, Mesopotamia, Armenia, and India, and African regions such as Ethiopia and Egypt, all of them with their saints and martyrs; we are then transferred to Europe, with Dalmatia, Russia, and the lands of Goths, Saxony, Hungary, Germany, Sweden. Italy is now close, with Naples and the Calabria. The French bishop continues his enumeration by listing Spoleto and Perugia and Rome and many other Italian towns, including Florence, Bologna, Siena and Venice, which preserved the body of St. Mark the Evangelist. After that, the text goes on with Spain and France and England, and ends up with «Ybernie», today's Ireland.

But no single reference to a Sibyl of the Apennines is found anywhere in Jean Germain's text.

So in the year 1449, in his *Mappemonde Spirituelle*, Jean Germain, also known as 'Primus Cambilunensis', never wrote the sentences on the Sibyl

of Norcia which were subsequently attributed to him by Francesco Maurolico and, a century later, by Father Fortunato Ciucci.

Fig. 8 - The excerpt on Italy from Jean Germain's *Mappemonde Spirituelle* (Français 13235, Bibliothèque Nationale de France)

So it was Maurolico, in 1568, who included in his book, the *Topographia Sanctorum Christi Martyrum*, the words concerning a Sibyl in the caverns of Norcia and her qualifiers as Ameria, Emeriam or Cimeriam. And he did not draw them from Jean Germain.

We have reached the bottom end of our search. In the next article, we will summarise the results of our ride across three centuries and propose further lines of study.

6. The search goes on

«Ameria, an Italian town set in the Sabine region», writes Francesco Maurolico in his *Topographia Sanctorum Christi Martyrum* in 1568. «From this town the author names the 'Emerian Sibyl', who others call the

'Cimeriam' owing to the uncertainty of the place; she lives in the caverns of Norcia, and she is different from both the Cumaean and the Tiburtine Sibyls». These words will be quoted by Father Fortunato Ciucci in his *Chronicles of the Antique Town of Norsia* written in 1650.

Francesco Maurolico, an abbot who lived in Messina, introduced his book with the statement that it was drawn from «Primus Cabilunensis, bishop and theologian, once composed in the Year of Salvation 1450 and now at last complemented» [in the original Latin text: «per Primum Cabilunensem, episcopum, ac theologum, Anno salutis MCCCCL olim composita Et nunc demum recognita»].

By following the faint clues leading to the unknown identity of 'Primus Cabilunensis', we have ascertained that 'Primus' was the pen name of Jean Germain, a bishop of the French town of Chalon-sur-Saône, who in 1449 wrote a *Spiritual Worldmap (Mappemonde Sprituelle)*, which made up the primary source of Maurolico's work.

Fig. 9 - Jean Germain presenting his *Mappemonde Sprituelle* to Duke Philip the Good of Burgundy (from manuscript Français 13235, Bibliothèque Nationale de France)

However, by consulting the ancient original manuscript of the *Mappemonde Spirituelle*, we found out that Jean Germain never wrote a single word about a Sibyl of Norcia, nor provided any reference to an Amerian or Cimerian Sibyl.

So, all such references to Norcia and a cavern and a Sibyl and a village named Ameria were included in Maurolico's book by Maurolico himself.

Can we assume that Francesco Maurolico did not just copy from Jean Germain, and introduced additional information instead?

Yes, the surmise is fully correct. It is Maurolico himself who tells the reader that he «complemented» the information coming from Primus Cabilunensis. Furthermore, in the foreword to his *Martyrologium* - which includes his *Topographia* - Maurolico writes the following sentence, which shows that Jean Germain's work was the primary yet not the sole source:

«In all that I definitely took great advantage from the 'Topographia' by bishop Primus Cabilunensis, who lived some one hundred years ago».

[In the original Latin text: «Ad haec multum mihi contulit, quaedam Primi Cabilunensis episcopi Topographia, qui centesimo fere ab hinc anno vixit»].

We have already shown that Francesco Maurolico had a peculiar interest in Sibyls, so much so that he included a specific section specifically dedicated to the sibilline oracles, «On Sibyls and other authors» [in the original Latin text: «De Sibyllis, et variis Authoribus»]. And he did like to elaborate on the subject by adding additional information with respect to what he could read in Jean Germain's manuscript.

As an example, let's consider Jean Germain's excerpt on the town of Cumae. Here is what the French bishop says (see figure):

«Town of Cumea. The seventh Sibyl was born here, she was called Cumaean when Tarquinius reigned [...] Here St. Abundius was bishop [...]»
(«Cité cumane. Cy fut née la septième Sibile appelée cumane autemps de Terquinius [...] Cy fut evesque saint Abonde [...]»)

So it is now certain that Francesco Maurolico did not draw his mentions of a Sibyl of Norcia from Jean Germain. Where did he take them from?

It is no easy task to provide an answer to this crucial question. As a matter of fact, Maurolico made use of a number of different sources which, after re-elaboration, finally made up his *Topographia*, as noted by many authors (Gabriel Le Bras among others). Therefore, this might be a topic for further study targeted at spotting the original source which Maurolico is quoting when he provides mentions of the Sibyl of Norcia and the Amerian or Cimmerian Sibyl.

Father Fortunato Ciucci, abbot Francesco Maurolico, bishop Jean Germain: three authors belonging to three different centuries who each took part, in one way or the other, in the long-lasting mystery connected to the Apennine Sibyl and her legend. A thrilling ride across time, which casts additional light over an enigma which is still enshrouded in darkness: one of the most fascinating legends of ancient Italy.

Michele Sanvico